

Life-Cycle Assessment of Solvent-based Post-Combustion Carbon Capture, Storage and Utilization (CCS/CCU) using Rotating Packed Bed (RPB) reactors

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ABSTRACT

Rotating Packed Beds (RPBs) have emerged as a promising solution for intensifying post-combustion CO₂ capture, owing to their enhanced mass transfer and reduced equipment footprint compared to conventional packed columns.¹ To date, no life cycle assessment (LCA) has been reported for RPB-based CO₂ capture. This work addresses this critical research gap by presenting a holistic LCA framework to evaluate the environmental impacts of RPB technology. This framework focuses on industrial post-combustion capture systems using the bench-mark solvent 30% aqueous monoethanolamine (MEA).

The proposed framework comprises a cradle-to-gate and a gate-to-grave stage. For the cradle-to-gate analysis (e.g., solvent production, RPB manufacturing, operation), two process configurations are evaluated: (i) a baseline RPB arrangement that includes an RPB absorber and desorber with intermediate heat exchange, and (ii) a thermally integrated configuration employing a high-temperature heat pump to recover and upgrade waste heat from multiple process streams to reduce the external heat requirement.^{2,3,4} For the gate-to-grave analysis, two additional scenarios are considered: (iii) utilization pathways through mineralization into precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) and (iv) sequestration with geological storage.^{5,6,7,8} Figure 1 illustrates the methodological steps for our cradle-to-grave LCA, highlighting the background system inputs (electricity, heat, chemicals) and the foreground unit operations (RPB absorber/desorber and heat pump integration), as well as the subsequent utilization or storage pathways considered in the gate-to-grave analysis.

These configurations along with the chosen impact assessment method enable a holistic evaluation of burden shifts and performance across the CO₂ capture, storage, and utilization lifecycle. The results are presented both globally and per configuration to facilitate comparison with alternative capture technologies.

Figure 1 Schematic representation of the methodological steps and system boundaries for the cradle-to-grave life cycle stages. The cradle-to-gate analysis includes the baseline RPB absorber–desorber arrangement with intermediate heat exchange and the thermally integrated configuration employing a high-temperature heat pump, while the gate-to-grave stage covers the utilization of CO₂ through mineralization into Precipitated Calcium Carbonate or its geological sequestration.

The framework is applied in a quicklime plant. The functional unit is defined as 1 ton of CO₂ treated, with specific system boundaries depending on the evaluated configuration. The production facility serves as the primary source of flue gas, which is treated by a carbon capture system operating at approximately 90% CO₂ capture efficiency with a recovery of more than 130 ton/day of CO₂. The methodology is developed in accordance with LCA established guidelines for CCS/CCU and draws from best practices in avoiding pitfalls specific to CO₂ utilization assessments.^{9,10} Environmental impacts are assessed using the ReCiPe (E) 2016 long-term impact assessment method within SimaPro v9.6, considering both midpoint (18 categories) and endpoint (3 categories) indicators. The ecoinvent v3.11 database serves as the primary background source, while foreground inventories are obtained from HiRECORD models validated against experimental data. Kantouros et al. developed and validated mathematical models to describe the processes occurring within an RPB reactor.^{11,12} The models, based on first principles, employed a rate-based, steady-state representation specifically developed for solvent-based CO₂ capture. A thermodynamic heat pump model was developed to identify the optimal working fluid, cycle configuration, and operating conditions needed to upgrade the available waste heat to the required temperature for solvent regeneration with minimal external energy input. For the CO₂ utilization, a steady-state, rate-based model was developed and validated experimentally for the synthesis of PCC nanoparticles using captured CO₂ and slaked lime slurry in an RPB.^{6,8} This model follows the first principles approach and Higbie’s penetration theory to incorporate carbonation kinetics and mass transfer phenomena. Table 1 provides a concise overview of the models, primary uncertainties, and software used for each process configuration.

Table 1: Overview of Configurations, Models, Uncertainties, and Software.

Process Configuration	Models	Uncertainties	Software
(i) Baseline RPB Arrangement	Rate-based, steady/dynamic PDEs for mass & energy Two-film theory (CO ₂ -amine)	2.5 % model-experiment deviation Assumes negligible solvent degrade & ideal mixing	MATLAB
(ii) Thermally Integrated Configuration	Vapor-compression (e.g., isopentane) cycle recovers “waste heat” Parallel compressors for condenser/lean-cooler heat upgrading to ~120 °C	Isentropic efficiency/approach temps may vary	HPC model (EES/ASPEN)
(iii) PCC Utilization Scenario	Reactive precipitation model (Higbie’s penetration, Ca(OH) ₂ kinetics) Pilot-scale validation for particle sizes ~45–60 nm	Maximum mean absolute deviation of 9.4%	Algebraic PDE/ODE
(iv) Geological Storage	MILP supply-chain design for capture/pipeline/injection	Future work	GAMS
Holistic LCA Framework	ISO 14040/44-Cradle-to-Gate/Gate-to-Grave (goal & scope, inventory, impact assessment, interpretation) ReCiPe (midpoint/endpoints)	Future work: Monte Carlo	SimaPro v9.6 ecoinvent v3.11

RPBs combined with heat pump integration technology has the potential for improved energy efficiency compared to conventional packed bed towers, underscoring the advantages of process intensification at industrial scales. The thermally integrated configuration further enhances performance, particularly in terms of auxiliary energy requirements. Associated environmental impacts indicate benefits in categories such as climate change and resource depletion, but also highlight increases in other categories, such as water depletion and metal consumption. Overall, this work expands the state-of-the-art by detailing a holistic approach that captures the multi-category trade-offs inherent in advanced RPB-based CO₂ capture. Such transparent and reproducible LCA results support informed decision-making and serves as a reference for comparative assessments against conventional capture processes and further developments in process intensification for CCS/CCU. Future work can incorporate this framework into prospective LCAs and techno-economic assessments for emerging technologies.

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